

PREVENTION AND COMBATING THE SPREAD OF POTENT SUBSTANCES AMONG YOUTH

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Abstract. The article provides examples from the works of researchers on preventing and combating the spread of potent substances among youth, and on adolescents with behavioral challenges.

Keywords: National strategy, youth, family relations, child-rearing, education and upbringing.

Within the framework of large-scale reforms being implemented in New Uzbekistan, special attention is given to promoting a healthy lifestyle among youth, developing their resistance to drugs and psychotropic substances, as well as ensuring the health of young people. We all know that in a changing world, various threats endanger not only the future of youth but also the fate of the entire nation. Along with protecting young people from the influence of foreign ideas, safeguarding them from various potent substances, drugs, and substances that cause drug addiction has become a pressing issue. At the same time, the emergence of new types of synthetic drugs and potent substances in recent years, and their easy distribution among the population, especially youth, through social networks without human intervention, necessitates bringing the activities of responsible state structures in this area to a qualitatively new level based on the priority principle "All efforts for human dignity." To achieve the priority goals of the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 11, 2023 No. UP-158 "On the Strategy 'Uzbekistan - 2030'" [1], as well as to prevent the illicit trafficking of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances in the republic, eliminate factors negatively affecting the gene pool by developing youth's "immunity" to their consumption, and organize a medical treatment system for young people suffering from drug addiction based on global experience, promising directions of state policy in this area have been determined. The Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 6, 2024 No. UP-73 "On Strategic Measures to Eliminate the Negative Impact of Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances on Population Health and the Country's Gene Pool by Eradicating their Illegal Circulation in the Republic of Uzbekistan" [2] has been adopted. According to the Decree, the National Strategy for Combating Drug Addiction and Drug Crimes in the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2024-2028, developed based on advanced foreign practices and recommendations of international experts, including those from the UN, has been approved. Accordingly, achieving the following goals within the framework of the national strategy has been defined as a priority task for all state bodies and organizations.

first: formation of "anti-drug immunity" among the population, especially women and youth, an intolerant attitude towards the use of potent drugs among schoolchildren and students, introduction of new effective propaganda and educational-preventive mechanisms aimed at preventing the spread of psychoactive substances in educational institutions;

secondly: development of a system for providing high-quality narcological care to the population based on new methods, implementation of targeted measures aimed at radically improving the system of early prevention, diagnosis, treatment and medical and social rehabilitation of drug addiction and substance abuse;

third: elimination of new methods of illegal circulation of narcotic drugs, psychotropic and potent substances and precursors (hereinafter - narcotic drugs), especially on the Internet, development of a complex of operational-search, investigative and expert-criminalistic measures in this area, primarily through digitalization;

fourth: creation of effective mechanisms for monitoring the practice of medical use of narcotic drugs by state and private medical institutions and pharmacies, as well as increasing the responsibility of pharmaceutical enterprises, entities engaged in wholesale and retail trade in narcotic drugs;

fifth: development of research activities in the field of drug addiction treatment and combating drug crimes, ensuring the implementation into practice and dissemination to the public of scientific research, conclusions, achievements and innovations in this area.

Today, the negative vices that threaten the future of the younger generation are not limited to tobacco, alcohol, or drug use. Recently, there has been an increase in cases of addiction to potent drugs containing psychotropic substances among many young people. In turn, this disease leads to the collapse of young families and children becoming living orphans. Currently, there are many cases of young people using certain medications for pleasure. For example, "Tropicamide," "Lyrics," "Regapen," "Zarex." Currently, you must have seen empty containers of eye drops called "Tropicamide 10 mg/ml" around pharmacies. So, why has the demand for this medicine been increasing lately? Is this medicine really being used for eye diseases? Unfortunately, no. This medication, which contains a potent tropicamide substance, is used for entertainment purposes. The increase in this vice, especially among young people, is a regrettable situation. According to experts, chronic use of Tropicamide causes psychological dependence, which is difficult to overcome within a few weeks.

According to B. G. Ananyev, the classification of young people based on psycho-physiological indicators of development includes the following chain of stages of change in the human life cycle[3].

As is known, on September 27, 2019, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 818 "On Streamlining the Circulation of Potent Substances in the Republic of Uzbekistan" was adopted. This decision approved the list of potent substances. The drug Tropicamide is also included in this list, and retail sales will be carried out only through pharmacies licensed for the storage and sale of narcotic drugs, psychotropic substances, and social pharmacies. Nevertheless, the demand for this medicine in the "black market" is growing day by day. In 2024 alone, during the work carried out by the State Customs Committee to suppress the illegal circulation of potent drugs illegally imported into the territory of the republic, the illegal circulation of 175,324 units of Tropicamide was suppressed. Criminal cases have been initiated under the relevant article of the Criminal Code and sent to the investigative body. Therefore, fighting against this vice today requires responsibility and vigilance from each of us. In fact, these drugs are used to treat diseases of the eyes or other organs of the body, and their trade is regulated by law. In pharmacies, these medicines must be sold based on a doctor's prescription. But, unfortunately, "resourceful people" are buying and consuming such drugs illegally. As a result, they harm not only their

own health, but also those around them. Today, it is true that the illegal purchase and sale of psychotropic (actually strong painkillers) drugs has increased in pharmacies and on the streets. Most regrettably, the number of young people and adolescents suffering from drug addiction is increasing daily, and these drugs are freely sold in open areas even in broad daylight. For example, a doctor is selling "tramadol," a powerful analgesic given to patients according to recommendations, in various ways. "Tramadol is called a narcotic analgesic. It contains narcotics belonging to the "opium" group and is considered a medicinal product that must be used for medical purposes. "Lyrica" - (Pregabalin) - an anticonvulsant, a derivative of gamma-aminobutyric acid. Pregabalin also has analgesic properties, therefore this drug is prescribed to patients with neuralgia. In this regard, new methods of drug promotion are emerging today. There are cases of advertising the manufacture of narcotic drugs, methods of their use through the Internet, mass media, by drawing text or graphics ("narcograffiti") of the address of an online store on walls and walkways. At the same time, cases of using information technologies and the Internet to find clients for drug trafficking are also increasing day by day.

According to experts, more than eight thousand such cases related to the advertising or sale of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances in the virtual space were identified in 2024. This puts on the agenda the issue of taking urgent measures to protect our population, especially the younger generation, from such negative phenomena. In order to combat this negative situation and improve the situation related to drug addiction, cases identified in the regions are being studied, statistical data are being analyzed, and necessary measures are being taken. In particular, in 2024, a special interdepartmental working group was created in our country, the main task of which is to identify and block the addresses of online stores engaged in the advertising and sale of narcotic drugs on the Internet, as well as to identify and delete "narcographitys" reflecting the addresses of electronic stores where the sale of narcotic drugs is carried out in residential areas. In these cases, it is clear to everyone how difficult it is to identify the guilty party, that is, the criminal. Therefore, the application of strict punitive measures against persons who have taken such a path serves the practical implementation of the principle of "law is supreme, punishment is inevitable."

M. Kogan defined it as "the totality of all crimes related to drug addiction committed by young people in a certain place at a certain time, as well as the totality of all young criminals guilty of committing these crimes"[5].

Thus, it can be concluded that potent substances constantly encourage young people to commit crimes. For example, according to a high-category narcologist, if these drugs are consumed arbitrarily, without medical supervision, they lead to self-dependence, and those who consume them become passive addicts and incite them to commit crimes. They are forced to take such medications regularly to feel healthy both mentally and physically. The worst part is that a person who initially takes one pill per day later consumes ten to fifteen, and after a certain period reaches the level of consuming up to fifty medicines. As a result, strong changes occur in the human body and psyche, moreover, excessive consumption of such psychotropic substances can lead to infertility.

According to studies, the roots of this disease, which is becoming widespread among young people, primarily go back to family and the environment. If upbringing is in place and psychological stability is not disrupted, no young person will resort to such futile actions.

After all, a country with healthy children has a great future.

In conclusion, it should be noted that, as Abdurauf Fitrat emphasized, "the fate of a nation depends on the state of the family in which representatives of this nation live. Where family relationships are based on strong discipline, the country and nation will be stronger and more orderly." Therefore, for a child to have an educated, mature, respected, and prosperous future, it is the parents themselves who are required to be morally and legally literate educators in the family today. At the same time, it should be noted that they are responsible to society for the well-rounded development of their children. Because it is more difficult to raise a child as a healthy-believing, righteous child who benefits society than to give birth to them. For this, it is necessary to create a system for preparing young people for family life, early prevention of situations that negatively affect the socio-spiritual environment in families.

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